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SYNTHESIZE, CHARACTERIZATION AND EVALUATION OF ESTERIFICATION REACTION OF P-HYDROXY BENZOIC ACID, P-NITRO BENZOIC ACID AND DIFFERENT AMINO ACIDS WITH PARACETAMOL

Jilla Lavanya, Adere Sushma, Errolla Sneha, Methuku Venu, T. Rama Rao

CMR College of Pharmacy, Kandlakoya, Hyderabad-501401, Telangana.

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ABSTRACT

Esterification is a fundamental chemical process with diverse applications across industries. This abstract explores the versatility and significance of esterification in various sectors, including food and beverage, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, polymers, and renewable energy. By forming ester bonds between carboxylic acids and alcohols, esterification enables the synthesis of ester compounds, which serve as flavourings, fragrances, drug prodrugs, polymers, and biodiesel fuel. The process offers flexibility in molecular design, contributing to innovations in product development, sustainability, and consumer goods. Understanding the applications and importance of esterification provides insights into its role as a cornerstone of organic synthesis and industrial chemistry.

Corresponding author

Dr. Jilla Lavanya

M. pharm, Ph.D.

Associate professor

Department of pharmaceutical Chemistry

lavanyabadugu@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Definition:

Esterification is the process of combining an organic acid (RCOOH) with an alcohol (ROH) to form an ester (RCOOR) and water or a chemical reaction resulting in the formation of at least one ester product. Ester is obtained by an esterification reaction of an alcohol and a carboxylic acid.

The process of esterification is a highly important one in the field of chemical synthesis. Esters are chemical molecules that are found in both natural and synthetic forms all over the world. Paints and varnishes, pharmaceuticals, plastics and coatings, biofuels like biodiesel, solvents like ethyl and methyl acetate, paints and varnishes, and those used as herbicides and insecticides are among the main categories of goods that are produced by esterification.¹⁻⁴

The reaction between carboxylic acids and alcohols runs very slowly and takes a very long time to attain equilibrium in the absence of catalysts. Among these are traditional solid acids like zeolites, super acids, heteropoly acids, supported chlorides, and ion exchange resins. Metal oxides such as CaO and MgO, metallayered hydroxides, and efficient enzymatic catalysts have also been applied in esterification processes. But many of these methods have drawbacks from the start, such as the need for expensive or hazardous materials for the reagents and catalysts, the creation of undesirable by-products, extremely acidic conditions, and the use of hazardous and toxic solvents, high reaction temperatures, low product yields, and extended reaction times.^{5,6}

Esters make up the majority of the chemicals that give fruits and flowers their distinct aromas and perfumes. Natural foods have a unique flavor and scent due to the complex mingling of many components, which is largely influenced by esters. For example, the natural aroma of oranges contains 34 alcohols, 10 carboxylic acids, 30 distinct esters, 36 hydrocarbons, aldehydes, and ketones. The food industry creates artificial blends that taste a lot like natural flavors in order to replicate them. Though artificial tastes are simpler than those found in nature, they are nevertheless combinations. An artificial pineapple mixture consisting of seven essential oils, seven esters, and three carboxylic acids is one example.⁷

Because their structures are simpler than those of other esters, the esters found in fruits and flowers are referred to as simple esters. Adding a carbon or another functional group will change the aroma that the ester produces because the alkyl and aryl groups on these esters are principally responsible for the scent that they release. Propyl acetate (C₅H₁₀O₂), for example, smells like pears. However, butyl acetate (C₆H₁₂O₂) has an apple-like fragrance despite having just one more carbon in its chain. Fatty acids are defined as long-chain esters, or those with long alkyl chains. Fatty acids are among the vital biological components needed for many biological activities.

Another means by which cells store energy is through the fatty acid pathway. The most prevalent form of fatty acids are created when three fatty acids combine with glycerol to form triglycerides. Triglycerides can diverge greatly and have a comparatively large molecular weight. The type and length of alkyl chains that make up their structure dictate their properties and purposes. Making soaps and detergents is one of the most widespread industrial uses for triglycerides.⁸⁻¹⁰

Since many commonly used pharmaceuticals and building blocks must have ester functional groups formed in order to be synthesized, esterification is widely recognized as a crucial transition in organic and medicinal chemistry. In addition, esters are widely used in the functional materials, fragrance, and flavor sectors. They are also widely found in lipids, natural products, pheromones, and other physiologically active substances.

One of the most often used techniques in the synthesis of esters is the classic acid-catalyzed Fischer-Speier method (catalytic HCl, H₂SO₄, etc.), which was first described in 1895. By combining an alcohol and a carboxylic acid, an ester is produced using the Fischer esterification process, which uses an acidic catalyst. The well-known Fischer esterification mechanism consists of several reversible stages. Good circumstances for the formation of products include a large excess of alcohol and/or the removal of water as a by-product of the esterification reaction.^{11, 12}

General reaction for formation of ester:

Ion-exchange resins are widely used in the processes of esterification and transesterification. It is a macroporous polymer composed of microspheres that has a gel-like structure. Typically, the active site (Brønsted acidity) of ion-exchange resins is a copolymer of styrene, divinylbenzene (DVB), and sulfonic acid groups. The concentration of the crosslinking component (DVB), which regulates the resin's surface area and pore size distribution, establishes the material's polymer structure.¹³

Trans-esterification is typically used to create biodiesel, an alternative fuel made without petroleum. Pre-esterification is required because the feedstock oil typically contains significant amounts of unwanted free fatty acid (FFA), which needs to be transformed into esters. There are usually expenses associated with neutralization and separation when liquid H₂SO₄ is utilized as a catalyst for pre-esterification. As a result, readily regenerable solid acid catalysts have drawn a lot of interest as a liquid acid alternative. The finest catalysts for a range of processes are believed to be carbon-based solid acids because of their exceptional mechanical and thermal resilience and inertness to chemicals. Sulfonated carbon is the most promising solid acid developed for FFA esterification.

A few drops of strong sulfuric acid are often heated with alcohols and carboxylic acids in order to identify the fragrance of the esters. Usually, each material would be heated in little amounts in a test tube that was briefly immersed in hot water.^{14, 15}

METHODOLOGY:

Schematic representation:

General procedure for synthesis:

Start with dry glassware. Assemble a water jacketed condenser, the 5ml conical vial equipped with magnetic spin vane; and an aluminium heating block equipped hot plate stirrer. Make sure that the system to be heated is not closed system have everything at the correct height and ready to go when adding the samples. Do not attach the water lines and begin passing water through the condenser. Weigh the required amount of selected alcohol and carboxylic acid. Saturate the alcohol with sulphuric acid in a flask. Add required amount of selected carboxylic acid to the flask. Add boiling chips and reflux the reaction mixture (sand bath is preferable) for 2 hrs. Allow the reaction mixture to cool to room temperature. Transfer the reaction mixture into beaker containing distilled water. Collect the obtained product by Vacuum filtration and wash with water. Purify the product by recrystallization.

The melting point of the pure compound was around 91°C.

Procedure for Cup-plate method:

Prepare nutrient media and transfer 20 ml into boiling tube, plug and sterile them. After cooling inoculate each boiling tube with 0.1ml of test organism (*Bacillus subtilis*). The inoculated agar media is poured into Petri plate and solidified. Make holes in the solidified media at the center by using sterile borer. Add 0.1ml of prepared antibiotic solution into the holes. Incubate the Petri plate at 37°C for 24hrs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identification tests:

S.no:	Identification tests	Observation	Inference
1.	Ferric chloride test: Drug + Hydroxylamine + HCl + FeCl ₃ ... Heat & cool.	Dark maroon colour is observed	Positive(+) for all compounds
2.	Phenolphthalein test: Drug + 2 drops of water + phenolphthalein indicator + dil. NaOH	Pale pink colour is observed by continues addition of NaOH	Positive(+) for all compounds

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR):

□ Compound:-1 (4-acetamidophenyl-4-hydroxybenzoate)

1593-[NH bend] – 1° amines, 1154-[CH wag]-alkyl halides, 3351-[NH stretch-1° 2° amines & amides], 2980-[CH stretch] – alkenes, 923-[OH bend] – carboxylic acids.

□ Compound:-2 (4-acetamidophenyl-4-nitrobenzoate)

1513-[CH-bend] - alcohols, 1153-[CH-wag]-alkyl halides, 1032-[CO- stretch]-alcohol, carboxylic acids, ester, 3370- [NH-stretch] - 1° 2° amines, amides, 1632-[C=C stretch] – alkenes.

□ **Compound:-3 (4-acetamidophenyl-2-aminoacetate)**

3397-[NH stretch] – 1° 2° amines, 914-[OH bend] – carboxylic acid, 1034-[CO - stretch] - alcohols, esters, carboxylic acids, 1432-[NO- asymmetric stretching] – nitro compounds.

✓ **Compound:-4 (4-acetamidophenyl-2-amino-3-methylbutanoate)**

3375-[NH-stretch]-1° 2° amines, amides, 1722-[C=O stretch] – aldehydes, saturated aliphatic, 1515 – [C-H bend] - alkanes, 1033-[C-O stretch]-alcohols, carboxylic acids, esters, 1629- [C-C stretch]-aromatics.

✓ **Compound:5 (4-acetamidophenyl-2-amino-4-(methylthio)butanoate)**

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4- ACETAMIDOPHENYL 2- AMINO-4-(METHYLTHIO) BUTANOATE LIQUID

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3393-[C=CH; C-H stretch] - alkynes, 2942-[O-H] - carboxylic acids, 1735-[C=O stretch]-aldehydes, satu.aliphatic, α β unsatu.esters, 1627-[C=C stretch]-alkenes, 1154-[C-H wag]-alkyl halides.

The Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) for the synthesized compounds:

- 4-acetamidophenyl-4-hydroxybenzoate
 - 4-acetamidophenyl-4-nitrobenzoate
 - 4-acetamidophenyl-2-aminoacetate
 - 4-acetamidophenyl-2-amino-3-methylbutanoate
 - 4-acetamidophenyl-2-amino-4-(methylthio)butanoate
- are shown different IR stretchings at various wave numbers.

Characterization of compounds (IR):-

S. no	Compound structure	Melting point	Molecular weight	IR stretchings
1.	<p>4-acetamidophenyl 4-hydroxybenzoate</p>	205 °C	271.2g/mol	1593-[NH bend] -1° amines, 1154-[CH wag]-alkyl halides, 3351-[NH stretch]-1° 2° amines & amides, 2980-[CH stretch] - alkenes, 923-[OH bend] - carboxylic acids.
2.	<p>4-acetamidophenyl 4-nitrobenzoate</p>	225 °C	300.2g/mol	1513-[CH-bend] - alcohols, 1153-[CH-wag]-alkyl halides, 1032-[CO- stretch]-alcohol, carboxylic acids, ester, 3370- [NH-stretch] - 1° 2° amines, amides, 1632-[C=C stretch] - alkenes.
3.		230 °C	208.2g/mol	3397-[NH stretch] - 1° 2° amines, 914-[OH bend] - carboxylic acid, 1034-[CO - stretch] - alcohols, esters, carboxylic acids, 1432-[NO- assymmetric stretching] -

				nitro compounds.
4.		290 °C	250.2g/mol	3375-[NH-stretch]-1° 2° amines, amides, 1722-[C=O stretch] – aldehydes, saturated aliphatic, 1515 – [C-H bend] - alkanes, 1033-[C-O stretch]-alcohols, carboxylic acids, esters, 1629- [C-C stretch]-aromatics.
5.		276 °C	297.3g/mol	3393-[C≡CH; C-H stretch] - alkynes, 2942-[O-H] - carboxylic acids, 1735-[C=O stretch]-aldehydes, satu.aliphatic, α β unsatu.esters, 1627-[C=C stretch]-alkenes, 1154-[C-H wag]-alkyl halides.

Biological evaluation of synthesized compounds:

Zone of inhibition:

Zone of inhibition of compound 1

Zone of inhibition of compound 2

Zone of inhibition of compound 3

Zone of inhibition of compound 4

Zone of inhibition of compound 5

Standard drug: Streptomycin .

Compounds	Concentrations (µg/ml)	Zone of inhibition (mm) E.coli		Zone of inhibition (mm) B.subtilis	
		Standard value	Obtained value	Standard value	Obtained value
1)4-acetamidophenyl-4-hydroxybenzoate	10 µg/ml	21.2 mm	18 mm	21.9 mm	16 mm
2)4-acetamidophenyl-4-nitrobenzoate	20 µg/ml	25.4 mm	29 mm	25.9 mm	22 mm
3)4-acetamidophenyl-2-aminoacetate	30 µg/ml	30.1 mm	22 mm	30.6 mm	16 mm
4)4-acetamidophenyl-2-amino3-methylbutanoate	40 µg/ml	33.2 mm	40 mm	34.2 mm	35 mm
5)4-acetamidophenyl-2-amino4-(methylthio)butanoate	50 µg/ml	40.2 mm	20 mm	41.4 mm	21 mm

The antimicrobial activity of compounds using B. subtilis and E. coli strains against standard streptomycin for the 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 µg/ml were done. In that compound-2 exhibits more potent against E. coli, compound- 4 exhibits more potent against E. coli and B. subtilis when comparing to standard streptomycin.

CONCLUSION

The present study was aimed for the “Synthesize, characterization and evaluation of esterification reaction of P-hydroxy benzoic acid, P-nitro benzoic acid and different amino acids with paracetamol”.

These synthesized compounds were identified with the help of identification tests like ferric chloride test (FeCl₃) that gives “dark maroon color” and phenolphthalein test. The compounds were characterized by fourier transform-infra red spectroscopy (FTIR) and Thin layer chromatography (TLC). The compounds were evaluated for the antimicrobial activity using B. subtilis and E. coli strains against standard streptomycin for the 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 µg/ml. In that compound-2 exhibits more potent against E. coli, compound- 4 exhibits more potent against E. coli and B. subtilis when comparing to standard streptomycin.

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